

INFORMATION RADIOLOGY DIAGNOSTICS IN TRAUMATOLOGY

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Actually. The rapid development of diagnostic radiology observed in the last two decades has opened up fundamentally new opportunities for clinical medicine, making almost all organs and tissue structures of the human body available for research. Radiation research methods have long been in second place in terms of the frequency of their use, second only to the most common and mandatory laboratory tests. Classical radiology in many areas of surgery, therapy, and cardiology no longer plays a leading role in the production of medical images. According to WHO, about 80% of diagnoses are made through the direct use of radiation research materials. In this regard, modern radiation diagnostics, which has various methods of visual control, is increasingly focused on comprehensive solutions to diagnostic and therapeutic problems using new methods. 100% of orthopedic and traumatology patients require examinations using radiological diagnostic methods.

Purpose of the study: show the capabilities of modern radiation diagnostics and improved techniques in increasing the efficiency of the diagnostic process and improving the results of treatment of patients with diseases and injuries of the musculoskeletal system.

Research objectives and Results: The widespread use of new technologies has not only improved the diagnosis of diseases, but also had a tremendous impact on the development of modern treatment methods and forced us to reconsider many established traditional approaches. Thus, the achievements of modern radiation diagnostics significantly improve the quality of diagnosis. They reduce the time a patient stays in the clinic and increase the efficiency of the diagnostic and treatment process, expand the horizons of scientific research and practical application of various imaging tools in clinical medicine and traumatology and orthopedics in particular. To develop and improve new methods of radiation diagnostics in traumatology and orthopedics, patients with various injuries and diseases of the musculoskeletal system were examined using radiography, ultrasound, CT, and MRI.

New techniques and methods for studying muscles using ultrasonography and computed tomography have been proposed. Criteria for assessing the condition of muscles during the lengthening process have been developed to predict the outcomes of surgical lengthening of the lower extremities. Adaptive-compensatory and recovery processes in the muscles of the thigh and lower leg after their lengthening culminate in the formation of new muscle-tendon relationships, which in their parameters approach the corresponding age norms. Here are several examples of the use of modern diagnostic methods in traumatology and orthopedics.

CONCLUSIONS. The use of modern methods of radiation diagnostics has made it possible to obtain new data on X-ray morphological changes in the joints and long bones of the extremities in patients with systemic and dysplastic diseases with a quantitative assessment of the severity of the pathological process. An algorithm for describing the distraction regenerate has been proposed and methods for quantitative assessment using CT and MRI have been developed. A set of indicators has been developed to assess the condition of the soft tissues of the limbs during lengthening, depending on the period of lengthening and the research method. CT made it possible to determine quantitative criteria for bone density in post-traumatic necrosis of free bone fragments and the end sections of the main bone

fragments in chronic post-traumatic and postoperative osteomyelitis. 8. It was found that a characteristic sign of a quantitative change in bone tissue density in patients with deforming arthrosis is its general decrease with a relative increase in the density of the subchondral layer, which are detected much earlier in CT studies.

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